

Notion of Potential From Special Relativity?

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In a previous note (1) we argued that a potential $V(x)$, which exists in Newtonian mechanics, may be written as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ (i.e. in a Fourier series). In another note (2) we suggested that the free particle wavefunction form $\exp(ipx)$ may be obtained from special relativity i.e. from the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. Thus in (1) we argued that the potential delivers impulse hits in a quantum mechanical scenario.

In this note we revisit the emergence of $\exp(ipx)$ from special relativity, which like quantum mechanics, does not include acceleration i.e. a frame moves at a constant speed. (In Newtonian mechanics a particle moving within a constant dx is also said to have a constant speed, but this speed differs in the next dx .) Given $\exp(ipx)$ in the context of special relativity, we consider the possibility of a system of impulse hits which may change p to p_1 etc i.e. a set of $\exp(ipx)$ s. This leads to an average $\langle pp \rangle = \{ \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) pp \} / \{ \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \}$.

A free particle satisfies: $EE = pp + m_0m_0$ ($c=1$). If one wishes to retain a constant E (energy), one may replace pp with $\langle pp \rangle$ and imagine a function $V(x)$ such that $-(E-V(x)) (E-V(x)) + \langle pp \rangle = m_0m_0$. With $p \rightarrow -i\hbar/dx$ one obtains the Klein-Gordon equation. Taking a nonrelativistic limit yields the Schrodinger equation.

We suggest the notion of potential may appear directly from special relativity together with the notion of a px dependent dynamic probability, namely $\exp(ipx)$ which is a quantum mechanical function. We further argue that the Newtonian approach ignores the information contained in $-Et+px$ and uses a smoothing procedure.

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics, which dates to the 1600s and is nonrelativistic, introduces the notions of momentum $p=mv$, energy $pp/2m_0$, force and potential $V(x)$ for a conservative force i.e. $F=-dV/dx$. Special relativistic results linked to constant motion frames emerged about 1904, 1905 yielding $EE=pp+m_0m_0$ ($c=1$) which reduces to $E=pp/2m$ in the nonrelativistic limit. Nevertheless, the potential still remains a Newtonian concept. In the 1920s, the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation was developed which used the form $pp/2m$ and also $V(x)$ from Newtonian mechanics with momentum being treated as an operator acting on a function i.e. $p \rightarrow -i\hbar/dx$. We ask: Can the notion of a potential $V(x)$ follow directly from special relativity?

Special Relativity

Special relativity deals with dynamics viewed from different constant moving frames. The idea of a constant velocity and not acceleration is inherent in this theory in the sense that the frame has a constant velocity which then appears in the Lorentz matrix. For example, Lorentz considered Maxwell's electromagnetic equations viewed from a frame moving at a constant velocity. In such a case a stationary electron would have an altered electric field and an additional magnetic one. If one introduces acceleration, the electron radiates.

In previous notes we presented a simple argument for finding the Lorentz transformation. We briefly present it here. Consider a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$. Viewed from a frame moving at a constant speed of $-v$, the particle moves at v so $x'/t'=v$. This suggests x and t must transform in a similar way. For example, if $t'=t$, $x'=vt$. Similarly m_0 will be seen to be in motion with speed v suggesting mv , i.e. momentum from Newtonian mechanics. To be more general one may consider $t'=F(v)t$ and an orthogonal matrix (with some kind of metric). This matrix applies to both (x,t) , but also (p,E) which is $(0,m_0)$ in the rest frame. The orthogonality suggests a constant magnitude of these vectors according to some kind of metric. Then:

$$\begin{vmatrix} F(v) & (v/b)F(v) \\ (v/b)F(v) & F(v) \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{vmatrix} \quad ((1)) \quad b \text{ is an unknown constant which makes } v/b \text{ dimensionless and } F(v) = F(v/b)$$

Acting on x,t yields: $t'=F(v)t$ and $x'=vF(v)t$ and on p,E : $p'=m_0F(v)v$ and $E=m_0F(v)$. Furthermore $((1))$ should apply to light because it also has a p and E , but no rest frame. Light is governed by $E=pc$ with c constant when viewed from different constantly moving frames so:
 $p'=Fp + (v/b)Fpc$ and $E' = (v/b)Fp+FE$. In the case of light, v and c are the only two speeds in the picture, so one may suggest that $b=c$.

For a particle with rest mass m_0 , if one associates m_0 with a concept called energy, then energy is not created or destroyed if the particle is viewed from a moving frame. Thus somehow E',p' must combine to yield m_0B where B is a constant to yield proper units. The idea of the unitary matrix already guarantees a constant magnitude of the vector (p,E) , one need only choose a proper metric which cannot be $(1,1)$ because $EE+pp$ grows with v and cannot equal a constant. $(1,-1)$, however, leads to: $-E'E'+p'p' = m_0m_0$ with appropriate constants i.e. c . In such a case: $m_0m_0 FF vv -FFm_0m_0 = -m_0m_0$ so $FF(vv-1) = 1$ or $F=1/\sqrt{1-v/c}$.

Smoothed-Over Approach

Even though special relativity is associated with constantly moving frames, one may consider a different frame i.e. a different $-v(x)$ in each constant dx . Then one has $p(x)$ and may introduce a function $V(x)$ such that: $-(E-V(x))(E-V(x)) + p(x)p(x) = -m_0m_0$ holds. In the nonrelativistic limit, this becomes $p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E$ or Newtonian mechanics. We suggest, however, that this is a kind of averaged picture of a more detailed one which exists which ignores information contained in a Lorentz invariant $-Et=px$. We discuss this more detailed scenario, namely quantum mechanics below.

The Idea of a Dynamic Probability

In the above section the notion of constant velocity moving frames was used to create a Lorentz matrix which converts the vectors (x,t) , (p,E) to (x',t') , (p',E') as seen in the moving frame. So far only constant momentum and speeds have been considered because one starts with a particle at rest and its dynamics follow strictly from the constant velocity motion of the frame.

Given the ideas in the above section one has the two Lorentz invariants:

$$-E + p^2 = -m_0 v^2 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad -Et + px \quad \text{where} \quad v = x/t \quad ((2b))$$

In ((2b)) a particle moves with $v = x/t$, yet one may make $-Et + px$ constant by considering jumps of $t_1 = \hbar/E * n$ and $x_1 = \hbar/p * n$ where n is an integer. These are not linked to v at all, yet define a resolution in time and space which depends on the magnitude of momentum. In other words, they define an internal clock and ruler which differs for each p magnitude, yet in another sense yields the identity of the momentum. Why would one ultimately want to physically establish the identity of momentum in space? From Newtonian mechanics, momentum is conserved and it would be convenient if this conservation were physically enforced by the particle itself. Creating an eigenvalue equation yields:

$$-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{which follows from} \quad \frac{d}{dx} (-Et + px) = p$$

One may note that x and t are treated as independent in this scenario i.e. the internal clock and internal ruler are independent. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ must be physically established/created at the same time the particle moves with an average speed of $v = x/t$ not linked to the internal clock or ruler, but rather to an external one. One may note that $\exp(ipx)$ s are orthogonal functions which in quantum mechanics are linked to the idea of conservation of momentum.

One may also note that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are not the same i.e. the eigenstate distinguishes direction of motion and is dynamical. Its magnitude is 1, so it is a kind of dynamical probability which ensures momentum conservation, we argue.

In other words we argue that important information is contained in $-Et + px$ which if dropped gives a smoothed over picture (i.e. Newtonian mechanics), but loses physically relevant physics (linked to interference/diffraction etc).

The Idea of a Potential $V(x)$

It is physically possible to give a particle an impulse and change its magnitude of momentum. This it seems would lead from $\exp(ip_1 x)$ to $\exp(ip_2 x)$ if only a single impulse is applied. Thus a statistical/probabilistic picture emerges. One may consider two averages:

$$\langle p \rangle = \frac{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) p}{W(x)} \quad ((4a))$$

$$\text{and} \quad \langle p^2 \rangle = \frac{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) p^2}{W(x)} \quad ((4b)) \quad \text{where} \quad W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$$

In a statistical picture one no longer has pp and p as in classical mechanics or even in $E = p^2 + m_0 c^2$ ($c=1$). Given that the energy equation describes a certain kind of motion i.e. one with a constant E , we retain ((4b)). We next ask whether one may consider on average a similar kind of constant energy equation with $\langle p^2 \rangle$. $\langle p^2 \rangle$, however, is a function of x , so one needs to introduce a function $V(x)$ such that:

$$[E - V(x)][E - V(x)] = \langle p^2 \rangle + m_0 c^2 \quad ((5))$$

This implies that for a fixed x , one has a kinetic energy $E-V(x)$ linked with a $p(x)$ i.e. $\sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}$.

Nonrelativistically, $E = p^2/2m$ which would be linked with: $E-V(x) = \frac{1}{2m} p^2$ ((6))

Given ((4b)) one may write: $E-V(x) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2W}{dx^2}$ ((7))

((7)) is the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Thus the idea of an x dependent function $V(x)$ which represents energy and is linked with impulse hits emerges directly from special relativity in a quantum mechanical framework i.e. one which does not ignore the information contained in $-Et+px$.

Demonstrating Impulse Hits

Above we argued that $\langle p \rangle$ emerges due to impulse hits, yet a smooth function $V(x)$ is introduced because $\langle p \rangle$ is also a smooth function of x . How do impulse hits appear? From ((7)) one may write:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2W}{dx^2} + V(x)W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((8))$$

Given the orthogonality of $\exp(ipx)$ s which ensures momentum conservation, one may write $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and use $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Collecting coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$ yields:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} a(p) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((9))$$

Thus $V_k \exp(ikx)$ delivers an impulse hit of k to $a(p-k) \exp(i(p-k)x)$ to create a weighted $V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx)$. Thus it seems the impulse picture, assumed a priori, exists.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the notion of a potential may follow directly from special relativity which yields the two Lorentz invariants: $-E^2 + p^2 = m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$) and $-Et + px$. The first holds for a constant p and E , but may be generalized if one uses $p(x)$ i.e. a different constant p in each constant dx . Then one may introduce a $V(x)$ such that $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2W}{dx^2} + V(x)W(x) = E W(x)$ which in the nonrelativistic case yields $\frac{p(x)^2}{2m} + V(x) = E$.

We argue, however, that such an approach bypasses information contained in $-Et + px = \text{constant}$. Although $v = x/t$, one may consider an internal clock with beats of $\hbar/E * n$ and an internal ruler with lengths of $\hbar/p * n$ where n is an integer. Such independent beats and ruler lengths (internal) yield a constant $-Et + px$ and establish the identity of p and $p^2/2m = E$. Why should an identity be established? We argue it must be physically established to ensure conservation of momentum. Mathematically one may create an eigenvalue equation $-\frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ with $\exp(ipx)$ representing a physically manifested dynamical probability. $\exp(ipx)$ s are mathematically orthogonal, but the physically created dynamical probability wave

physically creates this orthogonality over space. Thus instead of $p(x)$ we consider a system with dynamic hits and an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$ s i.e. $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. We use $-E + p^2 = m^2$ as the starting point and so create an average $\langle p^2 \rangle$ which is not equal to $\langle p \rangle^2$. Thus $\langle p^2 \rangle = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW/dx}{W}$ which is a function of x .

In order to retain a similar energy type equation we introduce a function $V(x)$ such that $-(E - V(x))(E - V(x)) + \langle p^2 \rangle = -m^2$ ($c=1$). This leads to the Klein-Gordon equation or the time-independent Schrodinger in the nonrelativistic limit. We show that the assumption of impulse hits delivered by $V(x)$ to various $\exp(ipx)$ s holds i.e. we take the Schrodinger equation, use $W(x)$ and $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and collect coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$. Using $\langle p^2 \rangle = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW/dx}{W}$ one obtains the Newtonian picture (in the nonrelativistic limit).

Thus quantum mechanics follows from including information contained in the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ (instead of ignoring it) and leads to the more detailed notion of a probability $\exp(ipx)$ which physically ensure momentum conservation through a physically created probability wave even though the particle moves with a constant $v = x/t$. In order to retain the dynamical probability $\exp(ipx)$ (i.e. retain this level of detail) we consider a situation in which impulse hits are delivered and thus use the quantum mechanical ensemble $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

References

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